

**RELATIONS BETWEEN CHEMICAL ACTIVITY AND ABSORPTION
IN THE ULTRAVIOLET OF CERTAIN ORGANIC MOLECULES.
PART IV. THE INTERACTION OF PHENYLHYDRAZINE
WITH THE CHLORO DERIVATIVES OF THE
SUBSTITUTED AMIDES OF MALONIC ACID**

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The interaction of the chloro derivatives of the substituted amides of malonic acid with phenylhydrazine has been studied under different conditions of temperature and the molecular quantities of the reactants.

The chemical activity of the chloro derivatives as measured by (a) the absorption in the ultraviolet (*cf.* part I), and (b) the velocity of saponification (*cf.* part II) and (c) the velocity of replacement of the chlorine atoms by hydrogen (*cf.* part III), has already been studied. This part is devoted to a study of the interaction of the following chloro derivatives with phenylhydrazine :—

(1) Dichloromalon-diphenylamide. (2) Dichloromalon-di-*p*-tolylamide. (3) Dichloromalon-di-*o*-tolylamide. (4) Dichloromalon-di-1:3:4-xylylide. (5) Dichloromalon-di-*m*-chlorotolylamide. (6) Dichloromalon-mono-*p*-tolylamide. (7) Dichloromalon-mono-chlorophenylamide. (8) Chloromethylchloromalon-di-*p*-tolylamide. (9) Chloromethylchloromalon-di-*o*-tolylamide.

The first member of the series was made to react with phenylhydrazine in boiling alcohol. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux on a water-bath for three hours at the end of which fine crystalline compound separated in the form of yellow bulky silky needles. The reaction is represented thus

(I)

Dichloromalon-di-*m*-chlorotolylamide reacted with phenylhydrazine in a similar way as shown below :

(II)

That the reaction proceeds as above is proved by the fact that on hydrolysis of compound (II), *p*-chlorotoluidine is obtained as one of the products of hydrolysis. This would not have been the case if the chlorine atom situated in the toluidine nucleus had been replaced by phenylhydrazine. Dichloromalon-mono-chlorophenylamide reacts in the same way as shown above when treated with phenylhydrazine. The most important fact which emerges out from the above reactions is that when phenylhydrazine reacts with compounds having halogens in the nucleus, the nuclear chlorine atoms are not easily removed but that the labile halogens attached to the methylene carbon atoms are removed (Chattaway and Orton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, 79, 461).

In the case of chloromethylchloromalon-di-*ortho*- and *para*-tolylamides, phenylhydrazine reacts to give a three membered ring compound thus :—

The above three-membered ring compound is fairly stable and resists decomposition when boiled with water. This is in accordance with the work of Perkin and Simonson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 98, 1165).

Further it is remarkable that these compounds are formed with great ease and the yield in each case is almost quantitative. The ease with which such three-membered ring compounds are formed and their comparative stability have also been the experience of other workers (Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 951, 305; Naik, *ibid.*, 1921, 119, 376, 1166.)

Again in order to investigate whether the chlorine atoms of the chloro derivatives of the substituted amides of malonic acid interact with phenylhydrazine successively or simultaneously, the following compounds have been selected for study :—

(10) Dichloromalon-diphenylamide. (11) Dichloromalon-di-*p*-tolylamide. (12) Dichloromalon-di-*m*-chlorotolylamide. (13) Dichloromalon-di-*o*-tolylamide. (14) Dichloromalon-di-1:3:4-xylylide.

The above chloro compounds have been reacted with phenylhydrazine in the cold. The first member of the series is obtained by the interaction of the dichloromalon-diphenylamide with phenylhydrazine. The mixture of the reacting substances is kept in alcohol for eighteen hours (overnight) when a crystalline substance is obtained. The interaction in this case proceeds as follows :—

The compounds 11, 12, 13 and 14 react in a similar way. From this it appears that the mechanism of replacement of chlorine atoms is of a graduated nature, one chlorine atom being removed easily and another with difficulty. To remove both the chlorine atoms a drastic reaction is necessary.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Interaction of Dichloromalon-diphenylamide with Phenylhydrazine

(a) Dichloromalon-diphenylamide (1 mol., 3.2 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (40 c.c.) and phenylhydrazine (3 mols., 3.3 g.) and the mixture heated under reflux on a water-bath for 3 hours when the compound separated. It was then filtered hot at the pump, washed with alcohol and ether to remove excess of phenylhydrazine and crystallised from benzene in yellow tiny needles. Whereas compound Nos. 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, and 9 were prepared in the same way as No. 1, compound Nos. 10, 11, 12, 13 and 14 (*vide* table annexed) were prepared by the following method.

(b) Dichloromalon-diphenylamide (1 mol., 3.2 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (60 c.c.) and phenylhydrazine (2 mols., 2.16 g.). The mixture was kept for 24 hours at room temperature when a compound separated in white tiny plates. It was then transferred into a crystallising dish and kept at room temperature for a couple of hours. It was then filtered, washed with alcohol and ether to remove excess of phenylhydrazine. Crystallised from alcohol it separated in tiny white plates. The properties and analyses of all these compounds are given below the annexed table.

No.	Name of the compound.	M.p.	Crystalline structure.	Solubility.	Analysis	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	Meso-oxalyl-dianilide phenylhydrazone. $C_{21}H_{18}O_2N_4$.	175°	Yellow tiny needles.	Soluble in benzene, chloroform; less soluble in alcohol, acetic acid and practically insoluble in petroleum.	N, 16.05%	N, 15.65%
2.	Meso-oxalyl-di- <i>p</i> -toluidide phenylhydrazone. $C_{23}H_{20}O_2N_4$.	185°	Yellow silky needles	..	N, 14.58	N, 14.50
3.	Meso-oxalyl-di- <i>o</i> -toluidide phenylhydrazone $C_{23}H_{20}O_2N_4$.	148°	Yellow shining tiny needles	..	C, 71.16 H, 5.60 N, 14.70	C, 71.50 H, 5.70 N, 14.50
4.	Meso-oxalyl-di-1:3:4-xylylidide phenylhydrazone. $C_{22}H_{20}O_2N_4$.	172°	Yellow crystals	..	N, 13.71	N, 13.50
5.	Meso-oxalyl-di- <i>m</i> -chlorotoluidide phenylhydrazone $C_{23}H_{20}O_2N_4Cl_2$.	196°	Yellow silky needles	..	N, 12.38 Cl, 15.43	N, 12.30 Cl, 15.6
6.	Meso-oxalyl mono- <i>p</i> -toluidide phenylhydrazone. $C_{18}H_{16}O_2N_4$.	195°	Yellow needles	..	N, 19.04	N, 18.92
7.	Meso-oxalyl monochloro-phenylanilide phenylhydrazone $C_{18}H_{15}O_2N_4Cl$.	189-90°	Light yellow needles	..	N, 17.73 Cl, 11.13	N, 17.70 Cl, 11.22
8.	1-Anilo-2:4-di- <i>p</i> -tolyl-carbamido-aziridine $C_{24}H_{24}O_2N_4$	145°	Greenish yellow needles	..	C, 71.83 H, 5.95 N, 14.20	C, 72.00 H, 6.00 N, 14.00
9.	1-Anilo-2:4-di- <i>p</i> -tolylcarbamido-aziridine $C_{24}H_{24}O_2N_4$	190°	Yellow tiny needles	..	C, 71.75 H, 6.24 N, 14.21	C, 72.00 H, 6.00 N, 14.00
10.	Phenylhydrazino-chloromalondi-anilide $C_{21}H_{18}O_2N_4Cl$.	179°	Tiny white plates	..	Cl, 9.27	Cl, 9.00
11.	Phenylhydrazino-chloromalondi- <i>p</i> -toluidide $C_{23}H_{20}O_2N_4Cl$.	210-11°	Tiny white shining plates	..	Cl, 8.44	Cl, 8.40
12.	Phenylhydrazino-chloromalondi- <i>m</i> -chlorotoluidide $C_{23}H_{18}O_2N_4Cl_2$.	218-19°	White shining plates	..	N, 11.56 Cl, 21.51	N, 11.39 Cl, 21.70
13.	Phenylhydrazino-chloromalondi- <i>o</i> -toluidide $C_{23}H_{20}O_2N_4Cl$.	158°	Shining white plates	..	Cl, 8.61	Cl, 8.40
14.	Phenylhydrazino-chloromalondi-1:3:4-xylylidide $C_{24}H_{22}O_2N_4Cl$.	206°	White plates	..	N, 12.14 Cl, 8.14	N, 12.43 Cl, 7.88

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